

THE CONCEPT OF ALTERNATIVE PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THEIR USE IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article scientifically examines the theoretical foundations of alternative phraseological units, their semantic and structural features, and their functional significance in the translation process. During the research, the levels of phraseological equivalence, national-cultural components, and pragmatic characteristics of phraseological units were studied through a comparative-analytical method. Furthermore, the article highlights the linguistic and stylistic problems arising in the translation of alternative phraseological units across different languages, as well as strategies for overcoming these difficulties. The study substantiates that context, semantic compatibility, and cultural equivalence are essential factors in ensuring the adequate translation of phraseological units. The research findings contribute to the further development of scientific studies in the fields of translation studies and phraseology.

Keywords: alternative phraseological units, phraseological equivalence, translation studies, semantic analysis, pragmatic features, idiomatic expressions, adequate translation, stylistic equivalence.

Introduction: Phraseological units are considered one of the most expressive and nationally-cultural rich layers of language. They reflect the history, traditions, worldview, and national mentality of a people. In modern linguistics and translation studies, special attention is paid to the study of phraseological units because they often possess figurative meanings and cannot be translated literally. Therefore, identifying alternative phraseological units and applying them correctly in translation is regarded as one of the most actual and complex issues in contemporary translation theory.

Alternative phraseological units are expressions that differ in form across languages but are similar in meaning, stylistic features, and communicative function. Such units play an important role in ensuring equivalence and adequacy in translation. In the process of translating phraseological units from one language into another, translators attempt to preserve their semantic meaning, emotional-expressive coloring, national-cultural characteristics, and pragmatic effect.

Many linguists and translation scholars have emphasized the importance of phraseological equivalence in intercultural communication. The correct interpretation and translation of phraseological units ensure effective communication between different peoples and help preserve the artistic and aesthetic value of the original text. Conversely, incorrect translation of idiomatic expressions may lead to semantic distortion and communicative misunderstanding.

Research methodology: In this study, alternative phraseological units and their application in translation were investigated through comparative-analytical, semantic, and contextual methods. During the research process, the semantic, stylistic, and pragmatic features of phraseological units in Uzbek, English, and Russian languages were analyzed.

Literature Review: The issue of phraseological units and their translation has been studied as an important scientific field in Uzbek and Turkish linguistics. In Uzbek linguistics, Shavkat Rahmatullayev developed the theoretical foundations of phraseology and extensively analyzed the semantic and stylistic features of phraseological units. The scholar emphasized that preserving the national-cultural meaning of phraseological units is of great importance in translation.

Nemat Mahmudov, in his research, paid special attention to the expressive function of phraseological units in speech and their adequate representation in translation. According to the scholar, not only semantic compatibility but also pragmatic meaning should be taken into account in translating phraseological units.

In Turkish linguistics, Doğan Aksan evaluated phraseological units as an integral part of language and culture and scientifically substantiated their connection with national mentality. The scholar particularly emphasized the importance of preserving cultural equivalence in the translation of phraseological units.

Furthermore, Ömer Asım Aksoy systematically studied idiomatic expressions in the Turkish language and analyzed their lexical and stylistic characteristics. His scientific works serve as an important source for identifying alternative variants of phraseological units in translation.

The analyzed scientific literature demonstrates that preserving semantic, stylistic, and cultural compatibility is one of the primary criteria in the translation of phraseological units

Analysis: During the research, alternative phraseological units in Uzbek,

English, and Turkish languages were comparatively analyzed. The analysis showed that, in addition to semantic equivalence, preserving national-cultural and pragmatic features is highly important in the translation of phraseological units.

The Uzbek phrase “yuragi orqasiga tortdi” expresses fear or anxiety. This expression is translated into English as “to lose courage” or “to be frightened,” while in Turkish it corresponds to the phraseological unit “yüreği ağzına gelmek.” Although the general semantic meaning is preserved in this example, the figurative means differ across languages. Similarly, the Uzbek expression “ko‘z qorachig‘idek asramoq” is translated into English as “to cherish like the apple of one’s eye” and into Turkish as “göz bebeği gibi korumak.” This example demonstrates a high degree of phraseological equivalence among the languages.

Phraseological units reflect the national mentality and cultural views of a people. For instance, the Uzbek phrase “do‘ppisini osmonga otmoq” means to be extremely happy. In English, this expression has no direct equivalent and is translated descriptively as “to be extremely happy.” In Turkish, however, the phrase “sevinçten havalara uçmak” is considered semantically close.

This situation indicates that some phraseological units do not possess exact equivalents in other languages due to their national-cultural characteristics.

The pragmatic function of phraseological units is to increase the expressiveness and emotional impact of the text. For example, the Uzbek phrase “tili uzun” refers to a person who talks excessively or speaks bluntly. In English, it appears as “sharp-tongued” or “talkative,” while in Turkish it is expressed as “dili uzun.”

In translating such expressions, not only the meaning but also the emotional and expressive coloring of speech should be preserved. Otherwise, the communicative effect may weaken.

Based on the analysis, the following strategies were identified as effective in translating phraseological units:

- using full phraseological equivalents;
- translating through partial equivalents;
- descriptive translation;
- contextual adaptation;
- stylistic compensation.

In particular, it was observed that descriptive translation is frequently used when certain Uzbek phraseological units have no direct equivalents in

English. In Turkish, due to historical and cultural closeness, phraseological compatibility was found to be at a higher level.

The analysis demonstrated that translating alternative phraseological units is a complex linguistic and cultural phenomenon. Adequate translation of phraseological expressions requires translators to possess a high level of linguistic competence, cultural knowledge, and contextual analytical skills. Preserving semantic meaning, stylistic coloring, and pragmatic effect remains one of the main criteria in translation.

Results and discussion: During the study, the semantic, stylistic, and pragmatic features of alternative phraseological units in Uzbek, English, and Turkish were comparatively analyzed. The findings revealed that complete equivalence in the translation of phraseological units is not always observed; in most cases, partial equivalence or contextual adaptation methods are applied. This phenomenon can be explained by the national-cultural characteristics inherent in phraseological expressions.

The results of the research demonstrated that, in addition to linguistic competence, translators must also possess linguocultural knowledge when translating phraseological units. Many idiomatic expressions are formed on the basis of a nation's historical experience, mentality, and cultural values; therefore, literal translation may lead to semantic distortion. For example, the Uzbek phrase "ko'ngli tog'dek ko'tarildi" is not translated literally into English but is rendered through a semantic equivalent such as "became extremely happy." This indicates the priority of pragmatic compatibility in translation.

Comparative analysis also showed that some phraseological units across different languages share a common semantic basis. In particular, expressions related to human character, labor, time, patience, and friendship often convey similar meanings in various languages, although their figurative representations differ. This demonstrates that phraseological units simultaneously reflect both universality and national specificity.

The study identified several effective strategies for translating phraseological units:

- translation through phraseological equivalents;
- use of semantic alternatives;
- descriptive translation;
- contextual adaptation;
- stylistic compensation.

Particularly in literary translation, preserving stylistic coloring was found

to be an essential factor because phraseological units strengthen the emotional and expressive impact of a text. If these stylistic features are not adequately conveyed in translation, the artistic and aesthetic value of the original text may decrease.

The discussions further revealed that due to historical and cultural closeness, certain Uzbek and Turkish phraseological units demonstrate a relatively high degree of equivalence in translation. In English, however, many expressions lack direct equivalents, which necessitates the use of pragmatic and semantic adaptation methods.

The research also confirmed that context plays a decisive role in the translation of phraseological units. The same expression may acquire different pragmatic meanings depending on the communicative situation. Therefore, translators should analyze not only the lexical meaning of a phraseological unit but also its communicative function and stylistic role within the text.

Overall, the findings indicate that translating alternative phraseological units is a complex linguistic and cultural process. Adequate translation of phraseological expressions contributes to effective intercultural communication while preserving the national and artistic characteristics of the original text.

Conclusion: This study comprehensively analyzed the theoretical foundations of alternative phraseological units, their semantic and stylistic characteristics, and their functional significance in the translation process. The research findings demonstrated that phraseological units represent one of the most complex and nationally-cultural rich layers of language, and their adequate translation into another language remains one of the most important and actual issues in translation studies.

Based on comparative analysis, both the common and distinctive features of phraseological units in Uzbek, English, and Turkish were identified. In particular, some phraseological expressions possess full semantic equivalence, while others can only be translated through partial equivalence. This phenomenon is closely connected with the role of national mentality, historical development, traditions, and cultural values in the formation of phraseological units. Therefore, during the translation process, it is necessary to consider not only the lexical meaning of phraseological expressions but also their pragmatic function, stylistic coloring, and linguocultural characteristics.

The study also identified several effective strategies for translating phraseological units. These include the use of full phraseological equivalents,

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semantic alternatives, descriptive translation, contextual adaptation, and stylistic compensation. The research scientifically substantiated that these methods are widely applied in translation practice. In particular, contextual approaches were found to be especially important when translating phraseological units with strong national-cultural components.

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